

EU programme to combat *salmonella*: 2008 results record a positive trend

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The EU-wide programme to control *salmonella* provides for all Member States to submit an annual report on the percentage of *salmonella*-positive flocks of breeding poultry and laying hens. To meet this requirement, all *Länder* (German federal states) submit their data to the Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) which then evaluates the data.

In 2008, in 0.8% of breeding flocks examined one of the *salmonella* serovars for which an EU goal has been defined was detected. 2.7% of examined laying hen flocks were infected with such pathogens. No *salmonella* bacteria were found in flocks in which the animals were raised. Germany thus complies with the EU goal to control *salmonella* and, in fact, exceeds it because those cases of *salmonella* that were found are below the EU target value. The data show that German measures against *salmonella* infections are effective; the consumer risk of a *salmonella* infection resulting from infected eggs or poultry was reduced.

The full version of the BfR Information in German is available on http://www.bfr.bund.de/cm/208/salmonellen_bekaempfungsprogramm_ergebnisse_aus_2008_verzeichnen_positiven_trend.pdf